

TWINNED
By Stars

D1.4 INTERNATIONALISATION PLAN

**WPI STRENGTHENING AND SUSTAINABILITY OF
COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL
TOURISM IN THE ORS**

TWINNEDBYSTARS

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION,
CIRCULARITY, AND DIGITALIZATION FOR ACCELERATING
NEW MARINE-BASED ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES
AND BUSINESSES IN ORS**

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¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

ANEN	Asociación Nacional de Empresas Náuticas
APMadeira	Madeira Promotion Association
ATA	Azores Tourism Association
CE	Consulta Europa
CMC	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias
CO	Project Coordinator
CTM	Martinique Tourism Committee
D	Deliverable
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
EC	European Commission
EMFAF	European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
EOI	Escuela de Organización Industrial
ES	Spain
EU	European Union
FR	France
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GVA	Gross Value Added
MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
NACE	National Classification of Economic Activities
OECD	The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
ORs	Outermost Regions
PT	Portugal
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats analysis
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Internationalisation Plan aims to enhance cooperation among SMEs in the outermost regions, specifically the Canary Islands, Madeira, the Azores, and Martinique, by fostering the development of innovative and sustainable maritime and coastal tourism products. The plan is designed to boost the competitiveness of these SMEs in international markets, leveraging the unique strengths of each region while addressing their shared challenges.

The document outlines the strategic steps necessary for creating a cohesive network of SMEs capable of co-developing tourism products, participating in international fairs and conferences, and improving their business capacity through tailored training programs. The key areas of focus include:

- **Contextualisation of Regions:** A thorough analysis of the maritime and coastal tourism potential in each region is provided, identifying opportunities for growth and the competitive advantages that can be leveraged through internationalisation.
- **SWOT Analysis:** A detailed Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats analysis of each region, setting the foundation for understanding the unique dynamics influencing the tourism sector across these territories.
- **SME Cooperation and Capacity Building:** Strategies to strengthen collaboration among SMEs, focusing on innovation, co-creation of products, and digital marketing. Capacity building is supported by training initiatives that are regionally adapted.
- **Co-creation of Tourism Products:** Identification of common themes such as astronomy and volcanism to develop integrated, cross-regional tourism routes that capitalize on each region's distinct assets.
- **Joint Marketing and International Promotion:** Development of a unified brand and marketing strategy to promote the products developed by SMEs across the regions, including participation in key international fairs and conferences.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation:** A framework for assessing the effectiveness of the internationalisation efforts, to track the impact of international activities, with mechanisms for ongoing improvement.

The plan serves as a roadmap to guide SMEs in these regions towards successful internationalisation, ensuring that tourism offerings align with global market demands while fostering sustainable development.

2. INTRODUCTION

The term ‘internationalization’ refers to all activities that put SMEs into a meaningful business relationship with a foreign partner: exports, imports, foreign direct investment (relocation or outsourcing), international subcontracting and international technical cooperation. In other words: business activities responding to the opportunities and challenges that globalization brings. It can take place at cross-border level, at transnational level inside the EU or at international level beyond the EU.

In tourism, entrepreneurial internationalization is considered a measure of the development (Lam et al. 2019). Tourism enterprises in general, and more specifically nautical tourism firms, operate in a highly competitive environment, searching for tourists to be attracted by its features. In this scenario, the undertaking of internationalization strategies may raise firms’ opportunities to work towards sustainable development, by focusing on those attributes that are more capable of nourish their image within the global market and are relevant to face competitors out of their natural environment of the industry and a key driver of innovation, competitiveness, and image enhancement (Schnitzer et al. 2018).

Coastal and maritime tourism includes activities on the shoreline and marine environments, primarily for leisure and recreation, such as enjoying beaches, sailing, diving, coastal landscapes, and cultural offerings. EU coastal areas are top tourist destinations, making coastal and maritime tourism the largest sector in the EU Blue Economy in terms of GVA and employment. Over half of the EU’s bed capacity is in coastal regions, generating significant national revenue, especially in Southern Europe. These regions also face high seasonality, with peak tourism in July and August.

Spain leads the coastal tourism sector in terms of employment contributing with 22% of jobs, followed by Greece with 19%, France with 13% and Italy with 9%. In terms of GVA, Spain leads with 23%, followed by France with 20%, and Italy with 11%.

Employment by Member State

Value Added by Member State

Figure 1. Share of employment and GVA in the EU Coastal Tourism sector, 2021. Source: The EU blue economy report 2024

In 2022, the European Commission's DG GROW launched the Transition Pathway for Tourism, detailing actions, targets, and conditions for achieving green and digital transitions and long-term resilience in the sector. This pathway calls for investments in circularity, improved data sharing practices, and skill development to ensure a qualified workforce.

The competitiveness of the EU tourism industry depends on its ability to become more sustainable. An October 2021 Eurobarometer survey showed that 82% of Europeans are willing to adopt more sustainable travel habits, such as consuming local products, reducing waste, traveling off-season, and choosing eco-friendly transport. Key interests when selecting destinations include nature (41%) and culture (42%), with many willing to pay more to support local nature and communities.

Coastal and maritime tourism actors should develop sustainable tourism in line with the EU's new blue economy strategy and the mission to "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030." The outermost regions (ORs) of the EU are highly dependent on tourism, accounting for up to 35% of GDP, though they face seasonal fluctuations and limited air connections.

2.1 THE PROJECT

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to transform European outermost regions (ORs) into internationally recognized maritime ecotourism destinations that leverage tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. Building on the success of previous Macaronesian projects, the initiative involves co-designing and refining marine ecotourism products and activities with SMEs on various islands. Practices like on-board marine environmental education, respectful wildlife viewing, and unique interpretive experiences have led to high tourist satisfaction and more environmentally responsible behaviour from both SMEs and tourists. TWINNEDbySTARS seeks to expand these successes across EU ORs, promoting green and digital innovation, strengthening existing partnerships, and fostering co-creation.

The project's success depends on tangible activities involving public and private entities representing the quadruple helix of the regions. Collaboration is based on established relationships from prior projects. The first half of the project focuses on analysis, mapping, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and training definition. The second half will concentrate on training execution, marketing and commercialization plan implementation, and product testing.

2.2 THE CONSORTIUM

The TWINNEDbySTARS consortium has professionals with extensive experience in the nautical tourism sector, both in the applied and research fields, in business support through clusters and chambers of commerce, or in the regulation and promotion of activities of this type, such as in the public administration sector.

This project builds upon a university & a research centre, regional governments from ORs, a maritime cluster, SMEs and a chamber of commerce, a marina, and an EU-wide boating association.

Table 1. TWINNEDbySTARS consortium.

Partner No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC/TIDES	ES
1.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT/ULPGC	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Asociación Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
4	Océano de Experiencias SL	NAUTIC OCEAN	ES
5	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas	CETECIMA	ES
6	Associação MarinaFunchal	MARINA FUNCHAL	PT
7	Associação Comercial E Industrial Do Funchal	ACIF-CCIM	PT
8	Secretaria Regional do Mar e das Pescas	DRPM AZORES	PT
9	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	CTM	FR
10	European Boating Industry	EBI	BE

2.3 THE WORK PACKAGE 1

The objectives of the WP1 are:

- Strengthening and sustainability of cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the ORs.
- Acting as a link between the quadruple helix representatives.
- Fostering the homogeneity of the network through the promotion of the certification (quality, tourism, environmental, Starlight...).
- Promoting the clustered participation in international fairs with the resulting product(s) within the "Trade Winds Starlight Adventure" and the promotion of a common brand image.

The tasks to be carried out to achieve these objectives are as follows:

T1.1. Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs, mapping of actors in the quadruple helix and stakeholder engagement plan.

T1.2. Homogenization and promotion of certification: enhancement of digitalization and circular economy.

T1.3. Elaboration and implementation of the internationalization and legacy plan.

This report, Deliverable D1.4 is carried out in the framework of T1.3 and aims to define an internationalisation plan for the nautical companies in the regions covered by the project, as well as the transnational promotion of the products created within the framework of the project.

2.4 STAGES OF AN INTERNATIONALISATION PLAN

All countries have policies to promote internationalization which are described, according to the consolidated text of Spanish Law 14/2013, of 27 September, on support for entrepreneurs and their internationalization, as "the set of actions developed by the public sector, together with the private sector, to facilitate and strengthen the international dimension of the economy and promote the presence abroad of companies and entrepreneurs as factors of stability, growth and job creation".

Internationalized companies experience productivity gains, improvements in management, better access to financing and are, in short, those with the greatest capacity to grow and create jobs. More than ever, internationalization is proving to be a key driver of long-term economic growth of the economy due to its relationship with competitiveness and productivity gains.

The best way to define internationalization actions for a company is to have an Internationalization Plan, which according to the Escuela de Organización Industrial (EOI) (Cano et al. 2010) is structured as follows:

Table 2: Traditional structure of an internationalization plan. Source: Escuela de Organización Industrial (Cano et al. 2010).

Phase	Description
Stage 1: Diagnosis of Internationalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal Analysis • External Analysis • International SWOT Analysis
Stage 2: Market Selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concentration/Diversification Strategy • Market Pre-selection • Market Comparison
Stage 3: Forms of Entry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entry Method Alternatives • Entry Form Selection • Channel Profile • Trading Conditions
Stage 4: Product Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of product/service portfolio • Product standardization/adaptation • Standardization/adaptation of service
Stage 5: Communication Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication tools • Selection of communication instruments • Budgets

Phase	Description
Stage 6: Pricing Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Transport and Logistics • Collection Management • Risk coverage • Incoterms • International Pricing • Necessary Documentation
Stage 7: International Offer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of the offer
Stage 8: Economic Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantification of commercial objectives and sales targets

The Internationalization Plan of the Outermost Regions of Azores, Canaries Island, Madeira and Martinique, is part of a broader project, and as such, not all phases of a model plan will be strictly followed. The development of this plan is closely linked to the final product that will be developed within the project framework. Specifically, the outcomes will be detailed in D3.3 – Report on the product developed, including a marketing & business plan. In this regard, Work Package 3 (WP3) will gather more concrete actions tailored to the final product being tested and developed throughout the project's life cycle.

2.5 SUBSECTORS WITH ACTIVITY IN COASTAL AND MARITIME TOURISM

For the project, the most important stakeholders, are the business entities. To define the entities that are part of the industry category, we have based our classification on the European NACE Rev.2 distribution used by (1) the Spanish National Association of Nautical Companies (ANEN) and the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM) in the study *Impacto Económico de la Náutica de Recreo*, (2) the categorisation described in the European IMPACTOUR project, (3) as well as the previous work carried out in the initiative financed by the INTERREG MAC programme called SMART BLUEF (MAC 2/2.3d/355), in which several of the TWINNEDbySTARS partners took part:

Table 3: sub-sectors and segments of activity for coastal and maritime tourism.

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
Ports and marinas	Private Nautical port managers Port services concessions
Services to recreational and sport boats	Repair and maintenance workshops Mechanics Radio electronics Nautical refrigeration

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
	Dry docks and winter storage Fuel supply Inspection
Manufacture and sale and purchase of recreational and sport vessels	Boat manufacturing Boat distributors Official services Accessories and supplies
Charter and maritime excursions	Nautical charter Maritime excursions Whale watching Fishing tourism and marine tourism
Coastal tourism and water sports activities	Scuba diving Snorkelling Freediving Open water swimming Sailing / foil sports: surfing, windsurfing, kitesurfing, and similar Light boat activities: rowing, canoeing, and kayaking
Services to coastal tourism and water sports activities	Sale and/or rental of equipment accessories for sailing, surfing, windsurfing, and kitesurfing activities Sale and/or rental of accessories and equipment for rowing, canoeing and kayaking activities. Sale and/or rental of accessories and equipment for recreational underwater activities: scuba diving and snorkelling.
Nautical training and qualifications	Academies Clubs Sport schools
Commercial services	Tour Operators Travel agencies
Investors	Investors
Active and experiential tourism	Active tourism SMEs Experiential travel SMEs

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
Business associations	Tourism and maritime clusters Tourism associations Regional business federations Chambers of commerce
Media	Regional, national, and European media Digital media

3. INTERNATIONALISATION PLAN OF TWINNEDBYSTARS

This Section provides a comprehensive strategy for enhancing the global presence of SMEs in the outermost regions. It begins with the **contextualization of the regions**, offering insights into the local maritime and coastal tourism landscapes. This is followed by the **identification of potentials and opportunities**, where the unique strengths and market possibilities of each region are explored. The plan also emphasizes **SME cooperation and capacity building**, fostering collaboration and enhancing the skills needed for international competitiveness. **Co-creation of tourism products** is highlighted as a key approach to developing innovative and regionally integrated offerings. Additionally, the plan outlines the importance of **participation in international fairs and conferences** to increase visibility and networking opportunities. Finally, the section covers **evaluation and monitoring** to ensure the internationalization efforts are effective, with continuous improvement based on measurable outcomes and market feedback.

3.1 CONTEXTUALISATION OF THE REGIONS

At this point, we present a summary of the characterisation of the 4 regions involved in the project, for a better understanding of the actions proposed in the internationalisation plan.

Canary Islands

Tourism in the Canary Islands is one of the fundamental pillars of its economy, attracting millions of visitors each year thanks to its warm climate, varied landscapes, and diverse cultural and leisure offer. This sector represents a significant part of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the archipelago and generates employment both directly and indirectly. The well-developed tourism infrastructure, ranging from hotel complexes to transportation services and recreational activities, has made the Canary Islands a world-class destination.

Within this general context, coastal and maritime tourism has a special relevance in the **Canary Islands, with 400,000 nautical tourists in 2023, the Canaries remain a top destination for nautical tourism, with a growth of 2.5%**. The islands offer a wide range of activities, including sport fishing, windsurfing and kitesurfing, benefiting from an excellent port infrastructure. This type of tourism focuses on the use of natural and marine resources, offering experiences ranging from diving and sport fishing to sailing and whale watching. The geographical position of the

islands and the quality of their waters make this sector a crucial component of what is called the Blue Economy, which not only contributes significantly to the regional GDP, but also focuses on sustainability and protection of the marine environment.

The Barometer of the Blue Economy in the Canary Islands 2023 developed by CETECIMA highlights the pivotal role of nautical tourism within the Blue Economy. This sector not only supports the overall economic framework but also emphasizes the importance of continuous investment in marine infrastructure to sustain this growth. The report underscores that these activities are crucial for the diversification of the Canary Islands' economy, creating jobs and enhancing the region's attractiveness as a prime destination for maritime tourism.

Martinique

Martinique, a Caribbean island territory and overseas region of France, has tourism as one of the cornerstones of its economy, accounting for approximately 10% of the island's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), according to official data from the French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE). This sector is a key source of employment and economic development, with a high dependence on coastal and maritime tourism due to the geographical characteristics of the island.

Martinique attracted **180,000 nautical tourists in 2023, an increase of 5%**. The island is popular for activities such as snorkelling, sailing and coral reef exploration, supported by well-equipped marinas and high-quality nautical services.

Martinique has more than 350 km of coastline and is famous for its beaches, coral reefs and waters ideal for sailing and diving, making it a favourite destination in the Caribbean. This type of tourism attracts a significant number of international visitors each year, especially from Europe, making a crucial contribution to the local economy.

Azores

The Azores archipelago, an autonomous region of Portugal located in the Atlantic, is known for its unique volcanic landscape and biodiversity, which has made tourism a vital sector for its economy. According to official data, tourism accounts for approximately 12% of the Azores Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Coastal and maritime tourism is one of the most important pillars due to the exceptional natural conditions of the islands, which attract visitors interested in activities such as whale watching, sport fishing, diving and sailing.

The Azores welcomed nearly **150,000 nautical tourists in 2023, representing a 4% growth over the previous year**. The islands are known for volcanic cave diving, whale watching and sailing.

The Azores have positioned themselves as one of the best destinations worldwide for whale watching, an activity that generates a significant economic impact and attracts tourists from all over the world. In addition, the region has been recognized for its commitment to sustainability, being a model of responsible tourism that seeks to preserve its valuable natural environment for future generations.

Madeira

Madeira, also a Portuguese archipelago located in the Atlantic, is widely recognized for its tourist attraction, driven by its subtropical climate, mountainous landscapes and rugged coastline. Tourism is one of Madeira's main economic drivers, contributing significantly to its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Coastal and maritime tourism plays an essential role due to the unique geographical characteristics of the region, which make it ideal for activities such as sailing, whale watching, diving and other water sports. The luxury marina in Funchal and Madeira's popularity as a departure point for international cruises further reinforce the relevance of maritime tourism in the local economy. These activities not only attract numerous international tourists, but are also fundamental to Madeira's economic growth, fostering job creation and investment in tourism infrastructure.

Madeira recorded a **3% increase in the number of nautical tourists in 2023, with a total of 200,000 visitors interested in nautical activities**. The region has a solid infrastructure with well-equipped marinas and offers activities such as diving, sailing and whale watching.

3.2 IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIALS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis is a crucial step in the development of the Internationalization Plan for the outermost regions. This analysis provides a comprehensive overview of both internal and external factors that influence the competitive positioning of these regions in the global tourism market. By identifying strengths and opportunities, the plan can leverage the unique assets of each region to enhance international appeal, while addressing weaknesses and mitigating potential threats. A thorough SWOT analysis is necessary to inform strategic decisions, ensure effective resource allocation, and tailor actions that foster sustainable growth and long-term competitiveness in coastal and maritime tourism.

[SWOT analysis:](#)

CANARY ISLANDS

Strengths:

- **Stable Climate:** The Canary Islands benefit from a subtropical climate, ensuring year-round appeal for tourists, enhancing visitor satisfaction and repeat visits.
- **Diversity of Activities:** A wide range of recreational options, including water sports, hiking, and cultural experiences, caters to various tourist demographics, increasing market competitiveness.
- **Infrastructure:** Well-developed transportation and accommodation facilities facilitate ease of access and enhance the overall tourist experience, promoting longer stays and higher spending.

Weaknesses:

- High Internal Competition: Numerous destinations within the archipelago compete for the same tourist demographic, which may dilute market share and increase marketing costs.
- External Competition: Competing with other Mediterranean and global tourist destinations may hinder growth, requiring strategic marketing and differentiation.

Opportunities:

- Growth of Sustainable Tourism: Increasing global interest in sustainability offers the potential for the Canary Islands to position themselves as a leader in eco-friendly tourism initiatives, attracting environmentally-conscious travellers.

Threats:

- Environmental Pressure: The fragility of the local ecosystem due to increased tourism may lead to degradation of natural resources, necessitating robust environmental management strategies.

MARTINIQUE

Strengths:

- Rich Marine Biodiversity: The island's diverse marine ecosystems attract ecotourism and scuba diving enthusiasts, enhancing its appeal as a premier nature destination.
- Deep-rooted Nautical Culture: Strong maritime traditions provide unique cultural experiences, adding value to the tourism offering and enhancing visitor engagement.
- Favourable tax context
- Quality of the infrastructure (Le Marin marina, the first marina in the West Indies, careening area allowing ships up to 440 tonnes to be taken out)
- Martinique is an important stopover in the Caribbean arc, recognised for its technical know-how, particularly for the rental, maintenance, and repair of pleasure boats.

Weaknesses:

- Increasing competition with nearby islands (Saint Lucia, Grenada, etc.)
- Difficulties in recruiting specialized personnel (construction, maintenance, preparation, reception, marketing, etc.).

Opportunities:

- Luxury Tourism Development: The rising global demand for luxury travel presents an opportunity to develop high-end resorts and exclusive experiences, targeting affluent travellers.
- Central position of Martinique in the Caribbean: possibility to transform the island into a platform for nautical industries and tourism
- Ecological transition of boating/preservation of the environment:

- The Marina du Marin has obtained the highest level of the port environmental management quality label from the French Federation of Marinas)
- Implementation of an Integrated Coastal Zone Management project (Baie Marin Sainte Anne)

Threats:

- Natural Disaster Risks: The vulnerability to hurricanes and earthquakes poses significant risks to tourism infrastructure and safety, necessitating comprehensive disaster management plans.

AZORES

Strengths:

- Preserved Nature: The Azores' unique landscapes and ecosystems provide a strong appeal for nature tourism, promoting biodiversity conservation and attracting eco-conscious visitors.
- Exclusivity of Activities: Unique experiences, such as whale watching and geothermal bathing, differentiate the destination in a crowded market, enhancing its attractiveness.

Weaknesses:

- Limited Infrastructure: Inadequate transport and accommodation facilities on some islands can restrict visitor numbers and diminish the overall tourist experience.

Opportunities:

- Potential for Infrastructure Expansion: Investment in transport and hospitality infrastructure could enhance accessibility and attract a larger tourist base, fostering economic growth.

Threats:

- Geographical Isolation: The remote location of the Azores can hinder accessibility and increase travel costs, potentially limiting visitor numbers and market competitiveness.

MADEIRA

Strengths:

- Developed Infrastructure: Comprehensive transport networks and accommodation options provide a solid foundation for tourism, facilitating easy access and enhancing visitor satisfaction.

- **Diversity of Activities:** A variety of recreational opportunities, including hiking, wine tasting, and cultural festivals, cater to diverse tourist interests, increasing the region's attractiveness.

Weaknesses:

- **Seasonal Tourism Dependence:** Heavy reliance on specific tourist seasons can lead to fluctuations in revenue and employment, challenging economic stability.

Opportunities:

- **Growing Interest in Ecotourism and Adventure Tourism:** The rising trend toward eco-friendly and adventure travel creates opportunities to market Madeira as an ideal destination for such experiences, attracting new visitor segments.

Threats:

- **Environmental Pressure:** Increased tourist activity poses risks to local ecosystems, necessitating sustainable practices to preserve the natural environment while accommodating growth.

3.3 SME COOPERATION AND CAPACITY BUILDING

This section focuses on strengthening cooperation between SMEs and enhancing their capacity to innovate, to co-create and compete in the global market. SME cooperation is essential for promoting shared growth, knowledge exchange, and the development of new tourism products across the four regions involved in the project.

The project emphasizes a collaborative approach through the implementation of training programs, workshops, and the establishment of cooperation platforms that foster synergy among SMEs. Capacity building is addressed by tailoring training to the specific needs of each region's tourism sector, with a focus on business management, digital marketing, innovation, and the development of specialized tourism products such as nautical, coastal, and thematic tourism.

In relation to Mapping of the industry actors, we take advantage of the work already carried out in T1.1. Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs, mapping of actors in the quadruple helix and stakeholder engagement plan., concerning the identification of the main actors in each of the 4 regions, from a quadruple helix perspective. See Annex I - D1.1 Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ROs and mapping of actors in the quadruple helix.

In terms of developing new skills, training pathways have been established at TWINNEDbySTARS through the development of workshops and courses focused on business management, innovation in tourism, digital marketing and development of integrated tourism products (astronomy, underwater heritage, volcanism).

In relation to training actions, we report on the training actions foreseen in the project mentioned below.

It is also important to highlight the WP2 actions, which will be carried out under the leadership of TIDES Institute, and which will significantly contribute to the improvement of SME cooperation and capacity building in the following ways:

Task 2.1 Co-design of training programme

- Personalisation of learning: Involving SMEs in the design of the programme ensures that training is tailored to their specific needs, encouraging greater participation and engagement.
- Fostering collaboration: The co-design process promotes the exchange of experiences and good practices between companies, strengthening cooperation networks.

This activity will take the form of workshops, to be held in each of the regions, involving nautical and coastal tourism companies, as well as new entrepreneurs in these areas.

Task 2.2 Development of training and self-diagnostic tools to identify innovation opportunities

- Autonomy and self-knowledge: Self-diagnostic tools allow SMEs to assess their current situation and detect areas for improvement, facilitating the identification of innovation opportunities.
- Continuous training: Providing accessible training resources contributes to continuous learning, enabling companies to remain competitive in the marketplace.

In addition to the actions already programmed, we also take the opportunity to include activities developed in other projects implemented by the partners, such as VOLTURMAC and Margullar I and II (projects co-financed by Interreg MAC 2014-2020), in the framework of which training programmes were developed for nautical and coastal tourism companies and interpreter guides related to volcanism on the south coast of Madeira and submerged heritage. An example of the programme is attached in Annex I so that it can be developed by partners in other regions and promoted as a new tourism product.

Business cooperation platforms are a key driver of competitiveness, innovation and sustainable growth. By enabling companies to collaborate rather than compete in isolation, these platforms create shared value, drive economic development and facilitate adaptation to an increasingly interconnected and complex world.

To boost internationalisation, cooperation platforms are great allies, as they facilitate entry into new or international markets, especially when companies with experience and distribution networks in different regions join forces. Through these alliances, companies can overcome trade barriers and expand their global reach without having to invest large resources in building infrastructure from its inception.

For SMEs in Madeira, Azores, Canary Islands and Martinique, the following cooperation platforms would be advised:

1. Regional Tourism Associations:
 - a. Madeira: Madeira Promotion Association (APMadeira).
 - b. Azores: Azores Tourism Association (ATA).

- c. Canary Islands: Turismo de Canarias and Sociedad Canaria de Fomento Económico (PROEXCA).
 - d. Martinique: Martinique Tourism Committee (CTM).
2. Networks of Regional Associations:
Platforms promoting cooperation between islands and Atlantic regions, such as the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance (A3M) created in the SMARTBLUEF project that can facilitate interregional collaborations.
3. Forums and Online Discussion Groups:
Platforms such as LinkedIn or specific social media groups focused on tourism, where professionals can share experiences and best practices.
Platform with the OECS (Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States) and the CARICOM (Caribbean Common Market).
4. Innovation Platforms:
Participation in innovation initiatives such as Erasmus for Young Entrepreneurs, which can promote knowledge exchanges and collaboration.
5. Exchange Programmes:
Explore existing cooperation programmes between the regions, such as cultural or business exchanges, which can be facilitated by governmental institutions or associations.

These platforms can help SMEs to strengthen their networks, access new markets and share good practices, contributing to the sustainable development of tourism in their regions.

3.4 CO-CREATION OF TOURISM PRODUCTS

Co-creation of tourism products is a powerful strategy that generates value for all involved agents. It drives innovation, enhances sustainability and enables tourism experiences to be more personalised and authentic. Enterprises that adopt this approach have a competitive advantage in a market where consumers are increasingly looking for meaningful and unique experiences.

To carry out a successful co-creation process of tourism products, it is important to follow a series of stages to ensure the effective collaboration of all the actors involved and that the final product meets market expectations. These stages are detailed below.

Identifying key actors

Already carried out within the framework of the actions implemented in the task T1.1. Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs, mapping of actors in the quadruple helix and stakeholder engagement plan., concerning the identification of the main actors in each of the 4 regions, from a quadruple helix perspective.

Identification of Common Themes

Selection of themes that can be explored in all regions, such as astronomy, submerged heritage and volcanism. The following are listed below by region.

MADEIRA

Astronomy

- **Potentialities:** Madeira has relatively clear and unpolluted skies, especially in mountainous areas such as Pico do Areeiro and Pico Ruivo, ideal for astronomical observation.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale watching:** Offer night boat trips with stargazing after the whale watching.
 - **Diving:** Organisation of diving sessions during the day and astronomical observation at night in remote locations.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Include stargazing activities in private events and sunset parties, providing a differentiated experience.

Volcanism

- **Potentialities:** Although volcanic activity in Madeira is less prominent, there are interesting volcanic formations such as the volcanic grottoes of São Vicente.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale Watching and Scuba Diving:** Complement the walks with information about the volcanic origin of the island and how it influenced the marine biodiversity.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Organisation of daytime tours to the volcanic caves and volcanic-themed events at night.

AZORES

Astronomy

- **Potentialities:** The Azores have some of the cleanest and clearest skies in the Atlantic, ideal for stargazing. Places like Pico Island are perfect for astronomical activities.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale watching:** Night walks with stargazing after whale watching, taking advantage of the remote location and lack of light pollution.
 - **Diving:** Diving days followed by astronomical observation nights, offering complete adventure and knowledge packages.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Private parties with stargazing sessions, complementing the sunset experience with the immensity of the night sky.

Volcanism

- **Potentialities:** The Azores are famous for their intense volcanic activity, with attractions such as the Furnas, volcanic lagoons and the Pico mountain.

- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale Watching and Diving:** Explanation of the volcanic formation of the islands during the walks and dives, enriching the visitors' knowledge of the local geology.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Organisation of visits to volcanic areas during the day and volcanic themed events at sunset.

CANARY ISLANDS

Astronomy

- **Potential:** The Canary Islands, especially Tenerife with the Teide Observatory, are known worldwide for excellent conditions for astronomical observation.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale watching:** Boat trips that combine whale watching and astronomical observation, taking advantage of the clear skies and the existing infrastructure.
 - **Diving:** Programmes that offer diving during the day and stargazing at night, promoting a complete experience of nature and science.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Private parties with telescopes and specialised guides for astronomical observation, providing a unique and educational experience.

Volcanism

- **Potentialities:** The Canaries are rich in volcanic formations, with attractions such as the Teide National Park in Tenerife and Timanfaya in Lanzarote.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale Watching and Diving:** Information about the volcanic origin of the islands during the walks and dives, explaining how volcanism shaped the marine biodiversity.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Daytime tours to volcanic parks and evening events with volcanic themes, combining nature, adventure and knowledge.

MARTINIQUE

Astronomy

- **Potentialities:** Martinique has potential for astronomical tourism due to low light pollution in some remote areas.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale watching:** Boat trips at sunset followed by astronomical observation sessions, taking advantage of the calmness of the sea and the clarity of the sky.
 - **Diving:** Offer packages that combine diving and stargazing in remote locations, away from light pollution.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Events that include astronomical observation after sunset, offering a rich and diversified experience.

Volcanism

- **Potentialities:** Martinique is famous for Mount Pelée, one of the most active volcanoes in the Caribbean, offering a rich volcanic history. It has been recently identified as an UNESCO heritage site.
- **Integration in Activities:**
 - **Whale Watching and Diving:** Complement the activities with information about the volcanic influence on the geology and biodiversity of the island.
 - **Sunsets and Private Parties:** Organisation of guided tours of Mount Pelée during the day and themed events on volcanism at sunset.
 - Combined destinations matching traditional tourism (green tourism, gastronomic tourism, memorial tourism...) with scientific tourism.

The integration of astronomy and volcanism activities into existing offers can significantly enrich the tourism experience in the outermost regions. These new activities not only diversify the tourism offer, but also increase the attractiveness of the regions, promoting a more sustainable and educational tourism. The combination of adventure, knowledge and nature can position these regions as destinations of excellence in nautical and coastal tourism.

Integrated Route Development

Creation of tourist routes that include activities in the four regions, promoting complementarity between them.

To develop integrated routes across the regions involved in the project (Canary Islands, Madeira Archipelago, Azores Archipelago, and Martinique), a strategic approach should be implemented that focuses on connectivity, infrastructure, and joint promotion. The first step is to identify key nautical assets and services in each region, such as marinas, repair facilities, tourist attractions, and cultural points of interest.

Coordination between the regions is essential to standardize services, ensure consistent quality, and facilitate smooth transitions between destinations. This can be achieved through collaboration between local authorities, tourism boards, and the private sector to develop agreements on service levels, maritime regulations, and environmental sustainability standards.

Promotion of these integrated routes should leverage digital marketing campaigns, participation in international nautical fairs, and collaborations with global boating and travel influencers. A unified brand for the routes can be developed, highlighting the unique offerings of each region while presenting the routes as a coherent and appealing package for international markets. Additionally, joint promotional materials, such as brochures, videos, and interactive maps, should be created to showcase the routes' natural beauty, cultural richness, and maritime services.

Finally, establishing partnerships with global travel agencies and maritime associations will help raise awareness and drive demand for these routes, ensuring long-term sustainability and growth.

Joint Marketing

Creation of a joint brand to promote tourism products developed by SMEs in the four regions.

To develop a Joint Marketing strategy and create a unified brand to promote tourism products developed by SMEs across the four regions (Canary Islands, Madeira Archipelago, Azores Archipelago, and Martinique), it is essential to align this effort with the broader objectives of WP3 in the project. WP3 includes a Marketing Plan for the product that will be developed, and the joint marketing activities should be integrated with this plan to ensure consistency and maximize impact.

The first step in this process is the establishment of a cohesive identity that reflects the unique cultural and natural attributes of each region while presenting a unified narrative. This identity will serve as the face of the tourism products, symbolizing quality, sustainability, and the distinctive appeal of the outermost regions. The identity should be co-created in collaboration with local SMEs, ensuring that it resonates with both regional stakeholders and the target international audience.

Joint marketing activities should focus on leveraging digital platforms, social media, and international travel forums to promote the brand and the tourism products it represents. This will involve creating a comprehensive marketing toolkit, including visual assets, content, and messaging guidelines that can be used by all SMEs involved in the project. Coordinated campaigns, such as shared participation in international trade fairs, digital marketing efforts, and promotional events, will enhance visibility and reach.

In line with WP3's objectives, the joint marketing strategy should include performance tracking to evaluate the success of marketing efforts and adjust tactics as needed. This approach ensures that the promotional activities not only align with the developed product but also support the SMEs in expanding their reach and attracting global tourists.

3.5 STRENGTHENING SME RELATIONSHIPS

To improve the relationship between the companies operating in the project regions, it is necessary that regular face-to-face and online meetings and workshops through the tasks of work package 3 to be carried out by the NAUTIC OCEAN and TIDES Institute partner:

Task 3.1: Analysis of coastal and maritime tourism products

- **Identification of Synergies:** By analysing existing products, SMEs can identify opportunities for collaboration and create tourism packages that integrate several offers, maximising their attractiveness.
- **Benchmarking:** Comparing products across regions allows learning from best practices and adapting successful strategies.

Task 3.2: Design and implementation of co-creation workshops

- **Team Building:** The workshops bring together different SMEs, facilitating the exchange of ideas and the co-creation of innovative products.
- **Networking:** The workshops create a space for establishing connections between companies, which may result in future collaborations.

Task 3.3: Product development, marketing and business plan

- **Supporting Innovation:** By working together on the development of new products, SMEs can share resources and knowledge, reducing costs and risks.
- **Co-marketing:** Collaborative marketing initiatives allow companies to leverage the visibility of the collective brand, attracting more tourists.

Task 3.4: Product testing

- **Collaborative Feedback:** Joint testing allows for valuable feedback from different stakeholders, improving the quality of products before they are launched.
- **Validation of Ideas:** Shared testing can help validate concepts and adjust offerings according to market preferences.

Task 3.5: Impact assessment and analysis

- **Measuring Results:** Joint evaluation will allow SMEs to analyse the impact of their collaborations, which may provide incentives for future cooperation.
- **Continuous Learning:** Sharing the results of evaluations encourages continuous learning, benefiting all companies involved.

Also, from the workshops developed in WP 2 and 3 of the project, agreements and alliances will emerge that will strengthen the transnational cooperation of SMEs in the regions involved. Moreover, these alliances can be established in the framework of existing regional initiatives of quadruple helix actors, such as A3M or NAUTICOM, taking advantage also of the new Interreg MAC projects, such as A3MAtlantic and INNOVABLUE and Interreg Atlantic Area, such as ATLIC. In the same way, based on the results of the workshops developed in WP2 and 3, a mentoring programme can be established in which more advanced companies can support those in the early stages of development.

3.6 PARTICIPATION IN INTERNATIONAL FAIRS AND CONFERENCES

Fairs and conferences offer valuable opportunities for companies in the coastal and marine tourism sector to network, promote their products and keep up to date with market trends.

When organising participation in these events, SMEs should be **actively involved**. It is essential that they consider participating not only as attendees, but also as exhibitors or speakers to maximise their visibility. In addition, it is intended that they **take advantage of Networking**, as these fairs are ideal to establish contacts and explore opportunities for collaboration.

The following aspects will be taken into account when organising missions to trade fairs and events:

- Participation planning: Identification of relevant international fairs and conferences in the coastal and nautical tourism sector.
- Logistical and Financial Support: Provision of logistical and financial support to facilitate the participation of SMEs in these events.
- Preparation for Participation: Training of SMEs to maximise the benefits of their participation, including training in presentation, networking and negotiation skills.

We highlight the following relevant international events in the coastal and nautical tourism sector that will take place in 2025 and 2026 in Europe and North America, which are the most relevant for the TWINNEDbySTARS project and the product to be developed in the project:

EUROPE

1. Fitur (International Tourism Trade Fair)

- **Date:** January 2025 and 2026
- **Location:** Madrid, Spain
- **Description:** One of the most important tourism fairs, where various offers are presented, including coastal and nautical tourism.

2. ITB Berlin (International Tourism Trade Fair)

- **Date:** March 2025 and 2026
- **Location:** Berlin, Germany
- **Description:** Leading trade fair in the tourism sector, ideal for making contacts and promoting maritime products.

3. Boot Düsseldorf

- **Date:** January 2025 and 2026
- **Location:** Düsseldorf, Germany
- **Description:** Fair dedicated to water sports and nautical tourism, where the latest trends and products are presented.

4. Barcelona International Boat Show

- **Date:** October 2025 and 2026
- **Location:** Barcelona, Spain
- **Description:** Leading event in the nautical sector, focusing on yachts, water sports and associated tourism.

NORTH AMERICA

1. American Boating Congress

- **Date:** May 2025 and 2026
- **Location:** Washington, D.C., USA.
- **Description:** Conference that brings together leaders in the marine industry to discuss policies and trends.

2. Florida Boat Show

- **Date:** October 2025 and 2026
- **Location:** Miami, Florida, USA.

- **Description:** Exhibition focused on boats and related services, relevant to nautical tourism.
3. **Annapolis Boat Show**
- **Date:** October 2025 and 2026
 - **Location:** Annapolis, Maryland, USA.
 - **Description:** Fair that presents boats and related products, ideal for connecting with the nautical tourism sector.

In Annex II an extensive list of international trade fairs and conferences of interest is included.

3.7 MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The approach for evaluating and monitoring the internationalization plan should be structured around continuous assessment. To ensure the effectiveness of the internationalization measures, periodic reviews should be conducted to analyse the impact of these activities in each outermost region. This includes assessing the direct and indirect effects of participation in selected trade fairs and international conferences on local economies, business networks, and stakeholder engagement.

This evaluation will be carried out through a post-participation survey at the selected fairs. Continuous feedback from regional stakeholders should also inform the refinement of the internationalization strategy, ensuring it is responsive to the unique challenges and opportunities of each region.

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ANNEX I. TRAINING PROPOSAL ON VULCANISMS IN THE MACARONESIAN ISLANDS

To train tourist guides and nautical tourism boat operators on the theoretical and practical aspects of volcanism in the islands of Macaronesia and Martinique, enriching their knowledge and skills to offer educational and attractive tourist experiences.

Course structure:

1. Theoretical Part: Introduction to Volcanism (4 hours)

- Basic Concepts of Volcanism
- Definition of volcanism and its importance.
- Types of volcanoes and eruptions.
- Effects of volcanism on landscape and biodiversity.
- **Volcanism in Macaronesia and Martinique:**
 - Geological history of the islands.
 - Characteristics of volcanoes in Madeira, Azores, Canary Islands and Martinique.
 - Relationship between volcanism and tourism activities.
- **Impact of volcanism:**
 - Effects on the marine and terrestrial ecosystem.
 - Opportunities for ecotourism and sustainable tourism.

2. Practical Part: Land and Maritime Visit to the Vulcan Coast (6 hours)

- **Land Visit:**
 - Tour of significant volcanic formations.
 - Observation of geological features (lava tubes, craters, etc.).
 - Identification of flora and fauna associated with volcanic environments.
- **Maritime Visit:**
 - Navigation along volcanic coasts.
 - Explanation of the formation of cliffs and sea caves.
 - Analysis of marine biodiversity in volcanic ecosystems.
- **Methodology:**
 - Interactive Classes:
 - Use of multimedia presentations and case studies.
 - Group discussion on previous experiences and expectations.
- **Guided Excursions:**
 - Practical activities supervised by volcanology experts and tour guides.
 - Spaces for questions and reflections during the visits.
- **Benefits for Participants:**
 - To increase their knowledge of volcanism and its relevance for tourism.
 - Improve their skills in guiding and educating tourists about the geology and biodiversity of Macaronesia.
 - Strengthen the supply of tourism services related to ecotourism and adventure tourism.

ANNEX II. LIST OF INTERNATIONAL FAIRS AND EVENTS

EUROPE

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	Date	18 - 26 January 2025
	Location	Dusseldorf, Deutschland
	Description	A fair dedicated to water sports and nautical tourism, showcasing the latest trends and products
	Website	https://www.boot.com/
	Date	22 - 26 January 2025
	Location	IFEMA – Madrid, Spain
	Description	One of the most significant tourism fairs, showcasing diverse offerings including coastal and nautical tourism.
	Website	https://www.ifema.es/fitur
	Date	4 - 6 March 2025
	Location	Berlin Exhibition Grounds, Berlin- Deutschland
	Description	A leading event in the tourism sector, ideal for networking and promoting maritime products.
	Website	https://asp.itb.com/en/home/
	Date	26 to 30 March 2024
	Location	FIL – Feira Internacional de Lisboa - Portugal
	Description	NAUTICAMPO is the largest and most prestigious outdoor activities event in Portugal. The largest Nautical Activities, Outdoor Leisure, Sports and Adventure event is one of the oldest in Europe.
	Website	https://nauticampo.fil.pt/
	Date	28 - 30 March 2025
	Location	Fira Barcelona – Spain
	Description	Spain's largest trade fair event aimed at the end traveller public and focused on both B2B and B2C. Here you will find the main travel agencies, hotels, cruise operators, transport companies and tourism services companies.
	Website	https://www.b-travel.com/

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	Date Location Description Website	01 to 06 April 2025 Hauts-de-Seine, Paris – France The event will be a showcase for all the latest national and international nautical expertise. https://www.nauticseine.fr/
	Date Location Description Website	May – Juin 2025 Fort-de-France, Martinique – France The South Caribbean boat show. Exhibition spaces on land and afloat to bring together professionals from the Caribbean marine industry. https://www.martinique-boat-show.fr/
	Date Location Description Website	Juin 2025 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Islas Canarias – Spain The Feria Internacional del Mar is a regional event of reference for the nautical and marine-maritime sector of the Canary Islands archipelago. https://feriainternacionaldelmar.com/
	Date Location Description Website	4 – 12 October 2025 Fira Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain A prominent event in the nautical sector, focusing on yachts, water sports, and associated tourism. https://www.salonnautico.com/
	Date Location Description Website	August to October 2024 Port Olímpic, Barcelona, Spain The prestigious sailing competition featuring the world's best sailors and teams competing in Barcelona. https://www.americascup.com/

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>6 to 8 September 2024</p> <p>Hamburg Marina – Germani</p> <p>The Hamburg marina in Wedel on the Elbe, Germany's largest sports boat harbor, will be the new meeting place for boating enthusiasts from Hamburg, the Elbe and the North and Baltic Seas.</p> <p>https://www.yachtfestival.de/en/hamburg-yachtfestival/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>19 to 24 September 2024</p> <p>Genova – Italy</p> <p>The International Boat Show is a must-attend event for both the international boating market and sea enthusiasts. Moreover, it is a global platform for institutional, technical and market comparison for the entire sector.</p> <p>https://salonenautico.com/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>September 2024</p> <p>Messe Friedrichshafen, Germany</p> <p>One of the largest boat and water sports trade shows in Europe, showcasing boats, yachts, and marine products.</p> <p>https://www.interboot.de/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>September 2025</p> <p>Port Hercules, Monaco</p> <p>A world-renowned yacht show featuring some of the most luxurious superyachts, accessories, and nautical services.</p> <p>https://www.monacoyachtshow.com/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>10 to 15 September 2024</p> <p>Cannes – France</p> <p>The Cannes Yachting Festival welcomes an eclectic range of more than 700 boats.</p> <p>https://www.cannesyachtingfestival.com/#/</p>

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	Date	19 to 28 September 2024
	Location	Southampton – United Kingdom
	Description	Britain's biggest and best festival of boating showcases a plethora of beautifully designed boats and products from hundreds of global marine brands. From kayaks to catamarans, SUPs to superyachts, there's a boat for everyone.
	Website	https://www.southamptonboatshow.com/
	Date	October 2024
	Location	Grand Pavois La Rochelle, France
	Description	One of the largest international in-water boat shows, attracting over 80,000 visitors and showcasing all types of boats.
	Website	https://grand-pavois.com/
	Date	October 2024
	Location	Zadar Cruise Port, Zadar, Croatia
	Description	A show dedicated to luxury yachts and the yachting industry in the heart of the Adriatic.
	Website	https://croatianyachtshow.com/
	Date	10 – 13 October 2024
	Location	Olympic Marina – Greece
	Description	A prestigious yacht exhibition showcasing premium yachts and marine products in a beautiful Greek setting.
	Website	https://olympicyachtshow.gr/
	Date	October 2024
	Location	PTAK Warsaw Expo – Poland
	Description	Poland's largest boat show, featuring boats, yachts, and nautical equipment from top manufacturers.
	Website	https://boatshow.pl/

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	Date Location Description Website	October 2024 Aprilia Marittima – Italy A unique used boat exhibition, where buyers and sellers come together in a marina setting. https://www.nautilia.com/

NORTH AMERICA

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	Date Location Description Website	May 2025 and 2026 Washington, D.C., USA Bringing together leaders from all sectors of recreational boating and fishing to advocate for the industry. https://www.nmma.org/
	Date Location Description Website	6 to 9 February 2025 Halifax – Canada This premier event offers a vast array of boats in various sizes and shapes, accompanied by exhibits featuring marine equipment, engines (diesel, gas, outboard, and inboard), marine electronics, accessories, as well as docks and dock builders. https://www.halifaxboatshow.com/
	Date Location Description Website	October 2025 and 2026 Annapolis, Maryland, USA A fair showcasing vessels and related products, ideal for connecting with the nautical tourism sector. https://annapolisboatshows.com/
	Date Location Description Website	January 2025 Boston, Massachusetts, USA One of New England's largest boat shows, showcasing a wide range of boats and marine accessories. https://www.newenglandboatshow.com/
	Date Location Description Website	February 2025 Miami, Florida, USA One of the world's premier boating events, featuring the latest innovations in yachts, boats, and marine technology. https://www.miamiboatshow.com

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>September 2024, February 2025</p> <p>Edison, New Jersey, USA</p> <p>Offers a variety of boats for sale, from small crafts to yachts, along with marine accessories and services.</p> <p>/https://www.jerseyboatexpo.com/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>March 2025</p> <p>Atlantic City, New Jersey, USA</p> <p>Annual event showcasing a wide selection of boats and equipment for boating enthusiasts.</p> <p>https://www.acboatshow.com/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>March 2025</p> <p>West Palm Beach, Florida, USA</p> <p>A world-class event featuring luxury yachts and high-performance boats in an exclusive setting.</p> <p>www.pbboatshow.com</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>September 2024</p> <p>Norwalk, Connecticut, USA</p> <p>Boat show offering live demonstrations, seminars, and a wide variety of boats and marine products.</p> <p>www.boatshownorwalk.com</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>October and November 2024</p> <p>Florida, USA</p> <p>Known as the largest in-water boat show in the world, featuring thousands of boats and exhibitors from around the globe.</p> <p>www.flibs.com</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>January 2025</p> <p>Hartford, Connecticut, USA</p> <p>Exhibition showcasing a variety of boats and marine products, ideal for boating enthusiasts in Connecticut.</p> <p>http://www.hartfordboatshow.com</p>

Trade fair logo or emblem	Main information	
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>January 2025</p> <p>New York, USA</p> <p>The oldest boat show in the United States, offering the latest in boating and water sports.</p> <p>http://www.nyboatshow.com</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>Dates TBD</p> <p>Baltimore, Maryland, USA</p> <p>Event that brings together boating enthusiasts and professionals with displays of boats and accessories.</p> <p>www.baltimoreboatshow.com</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>September 2024</p> <p>Lakewood, New Jersey, USA</p> <p>Regional event highlighting the latest boats and nautical equipment available on the New Jersey coast.</p> <p>https://www.jerseyboatexpo.com/jersey-shore-boat-expo/</p>
	<p>Date</p> <p>Location</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Website</p>	<p>January 2025</p> <p>Toronto, Ontario, Canada</p> <p>Canada's largest boat show and one of North America's premier boating events, showcasing a wide range of boats, equipment, and marine accessories.</p> <p>www.torontoboatshow.com</p>

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